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List of Abbreviations

2FA	Two-Factor Authentication
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HPC	High-Performance Computing
NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement
PM	Person-Month
RAM	Random Access Memory
SFTP	SSH File Transfer Protocol
SSH	Secure Shell
TOTP	Time-Based One-Time Password
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable provides the first version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the TURING project, funded under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme. The TURING DMP follows the Guidelines on Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) Data Management applicable to Horizon Europe projects and is aligned with the template and recommendations provided by the European Commission.

As the project progresses, this DMP will be updated to reflect significant changes that may arise with respect to the data sources used within the project, as well as any updates to data management policies, methodologies, and applicable legal or ethical requirements. In particular, updated versions of the DMP are planned at M18 and M36 of the project. The DMP is therefore considered a living document that will evolve throughout the project lifecycle.

The main objective of this deliverable is to provide an overview of the key data management policies adopted by the TURING consortium for the datasets generated, collected, and processed during the project. The DMP describes how data will be collected and generated, how they will be stored and protected, and under which conditions they will be made accessible to relevant stakeholders, including consortium partners and, where applicable, the wider research community.

Furthermore, the DMP details how and which datasets will comply with the FAIR data management principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), while taking into account legal, ethical, security, and contractual constraints. It also outlines the procedures for data curation, documentation, and preservation during and after the project lifetime, ensuring the long-term value, usability, and integrity of the TURING project data assets.

1. Introduction

The TURING project involves the generation, collection, and processing of heterogeneous datasets across multiple technical and scientific domains. These data support the development, validation, and evaluation of AI-based methods and tools within the project, as well as dissemination and exploitation activities. In addition, the project generates trained AI models and related digital research artefacts derived from these datasets, which are considered research outputs and fall within the scope of this DMP.

Given the diversity, volume, and potential sensitivity of the data involved, a structured and well-defined data management approach is required to ensure alignment with the FAIR principles [7], compliance with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR) [4], and adherence to the Open Science obligations defined in the Horizon Europe Model Grant Agreement [3].

This DMP provides the framework for managing research data and related digital research artefacts, including trained AI models where applicable, throughout the TURING project lifecycle, from data creation to long-term preservation. It establishes common principles and practices to be followed by all consortium partners, ensuring consistency, transparency, and responsible handling of data while enabling data sharing and reuse where appropriate.

1.1 Purpose of the document

This document presents the first version of the DMP for the TURING project. The purpose of the DMP is to describe how data generated, collected, and processed during the project will be managed throughout their lifecycle, including data collection, storage, access, sharing, preservation, and reuse.

The DMP is developed in accordance with the FAIR Data Management principles[7] and the guidelines provided by the European Commission for Horizon Europe projects. It defines the policies, procedures, and responsibilities adopted by the TURING consortium to ensure that research data are handled in a transparent, secure, and compliant manner.

Furthermore, the DMP aims to balance open science objectives with the protection of sensitive, confidential, or security-relevant data, following the principle that data should be as open as possible and as closed as necessary. The document is considered a living deliverable and will be updated during the project to reflect changes in data sources, methodologies, and regulatory or ethical requirements.

1.2 Intended readership

This deliverable is primarily intended for the European Commission, project reviewers, and officers responsible for monitoring the implementation of the TURING project. It also serves as a reference document for all consortium partners involved in data generation, processing, and management

activities.

Additionally, the DMP may be consulted by external stakeholders, such as researchers, data managers, and policy makers, who are interested in understanding the data management approach adopted within the TURING project. Where applicable, the document supports transparency and accountability with respect to the project's compliance with FAIR data principles, ethical standards, and legal obligations.

1.3 Relationship with other TURING WPs and managerial organization

Data management activities in TURING are closely linked to the project's overall work plan and governance structure. The DMP supports data-related activities across the technical WPs that generate, process, or analyse datasets, including those related to AI model development, validation, and evaluation.

Project coordination and governance activities, carried out under the management WP, provide oversight to ensure that data management practices are consistently applied across the consortium. Ethical, legal, and data protection aspects are addressed in coordination with dedicated tasks focusing on ethics and trustworthy AI, ensuring compliance with applicable regulations and project commitments.

The DMP complements other project deliverables by providing a unified framework for handling data across WP, facilitating coordination among partners, and supporting the efficient and responsible use of data throughout the project lifecycle.

The Data Manager of the TURING project is Ioannis Morianos (DIE), who is responsible for coordinating and overseeing all data management activities within the project, including the implementation and periodic update of the DMP. The Data Manager ensures alignment with Horizon Europe requirements, monitors compliance with FAIR principles, and supports partners in the proper handling, documentation, storage, and sharing of data and related digital research artefacts.

Each Work Package (WP) Leader is responsible for supervising the data generation and processing activities within their respective WP and for ensuring that datasets and AI models produced are managed in accordance with this DMP. The Project Coordinator maintains overall oversight and ensures compliance with the Grant Agreement and consortium-level governance procedures.

Decisions regarding data classification, access rights, sharing conditions, and long-term preservation are taken jointly by the Data Manager, the relevant WP Leader, and the partner generating the data, under the supervision of the Project Coordinator.

1.4 Structure of the document

The remainder of this document is organised as follows. Section 2 provides a summary of the datasets generated or used within the TURING project, including metadata descriptions, data sources, processing procedures, and access conditions. Section 3 describes how the project com-

plies with FAIR data management principles, detailing measures adopted to ensure that datasets are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable, while respecting legal, ethical, and contractual constraints. Section 4 outlines the allocation of computational and storage resources supporting data management activities within the project. Section 5 presents the data security measures applied to protect datasets throughout their lifecycle, including access control, authentication, encryption, monitoring, and backup procedures. Section 6 addresses ethics, privacy, and trustworthy AI considerations, including compliance with data protection regulations and governance mechanisms for responsible data and AI usage. Finally, Section 7 summarises the main conclusions and reiterates that the DMP is a living document that will be updated throughout the project lifecycle to reflect evolving requirements and datasets.

2. Data Summary

During the lifetime of the TURING project, several datasets will be generated and collected in support of research, development, validation, and evaluation activities. These datasets originate from different use cases and cover a range of data types, including experimental data, simulation outputs, benchmark datasets, configuration files, and associated metadata. Depending on legal, ethical, security, and contractual constraints, datasets produced within the TURING project are classified according to their level of accessibility as follows:

- **Open Access:** The dataset is either already publicly available or is planned to be made openly available at a later stage of the project, in accordance with Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) principles and Horizon Europe Open Science requirements.
- **Confidential:** The dataset is accessible only to consortium members and will not be released to the broader research community due to confidentiality, intellectual property, or contractual restrictions.
- **Closed Access:** The dataset remains on the premises of the data provider and access is limited to specific authorised persons within the consortium, subject to the signing of a Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA).

For each dataset generated or collected within the project, a structured metadata description is provided in the following subsections. These dataset metadata tables capture essential information regarding the content, origin, format, access conditions, ethical considerations, and preservation strategy of the datasets, and serve as the primary reference for data management within the TURING project.

As this deliverable represents the preliminary version of the Data Management Plan, the list of datasets and their corresponding metadata descriptions may be further extended, refined, or updated in subsequent versions of the DMP, in particular in the updates planned at later stages of the project, to reflect the actual data generated and evolving project requirements.

2.1 Dataset 1 - ERA5

Table 1: ERA5 Metadata

Field	Description
Title	ERA5
Responsible Partner	Météo-France
DOI	10.24381/cds.143582cf
Dataset Description	ERA5 is the fifth generation ECMWF atmospheric reanalysis of the global climate covering the period from January 1940 to present. It provides hourly estimates of a large number of atmospheric, land and oceanic climate variables. The data cover the Earth on a 31km grid and resolve the atmosphere using 137 levels from the surface up to height of 80km.
Work Package	WP3
Related Use Case	Weather
Source	Produced by the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) at ECMWF.
Processing	Regridding into regular lat-lon.
Repository	Access to ERA5 is provided through the Climate Data Store Application Program Interface (CDS API).
Language	English
Code List	Not applicable
Type	Gridded
Format	GRIB Alternatively, ready-to-use versions of (a subset of) ERA5 have been published in the Zarr format, by ECMWF and WeatherBench2.
Size	The entire ERA5 dataset is around 5 PB. Smaller subsets can be used for training (~ 5TB).
Keywords	Atmosphere, reanalysis, globe
Version	Not applicable
Date of Repository Submission	2023-05-25
Necessary Software	Different python libraries can be used, an example is earthkit https://earthkit.ecmwf.int/
Rights	Access provided through the CDS API. CC-BY licence.
Re-use	Pre-existing dataset
Data privacy	The dataset contains no personal data

2.2 Dataset 2 - ARRA

Table 2: ARRA Metadata

Field	Description
Title	ARRA
Responsible Partner	Météo-France
DOI	Not yet applicable
Dataset Description	ARRA is the first reanalysis of the regional climate covering the period from 1962 to 2020 over Western Europe. It provides 3-hourly estimates of a large number of atmospheric and land variables. The data cover a Western Europe domain on a 1.3km grid and several pressure levels.
Work Package	WP4
Related Use Case	Weather
Source	Produced by Météo-France using the AROME numerical model.
Processing	Regridding into regular lat-lon.
Repository	not yet available
Language	English, French
Code List	Not applicable
Type	Gridded
Format	GRIB
Size	Complete dataset ~ 150 TB. Smaller subsets will be provided.
Keywords	Atmosphere, reanalysis, regional, high resolution
Version	Not applicable
Date of Repository Submission	Not applicable
Necessary Software	Python libraries
Rights	Private data, property of Météo-France. Access provided to project partners only.
Re-use	Pre-existing dataset
Data privacy	The dataset contains no personal data

2.3 Dataset 3 - Calo Challenge

Table 3: CaloChallenge Metadata

Field	Description
Title	Calo Challenge Dataset 2 & Dataset 3
Responsible Partner	CERN
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.6366270 & 10.5281/zenodo.6366323
Dataset Description	Datasets 2 and 3 from the Fast Calorimeter Simulation Challenge 2022 focus on high-granularity electron showers within a simplified, collider-style detector geometry. Both datasets utilize a sampling calorimeter composed of 45 concentric cylindrical layers of alternating active silicon (0.3 mm) and passive tungsten (1.4 mm).
Work Package	WP3
Related Use Case	Particle physics
Source	The datasets are produced using GEANT4, a physics-based Monte Carlo Simulator
Processing	No specific pre-processing is required.
Repository	The data can be accessed directly through zenodo
Language	English
Code List	Not applicable
Type	Voxelised point cloud data
Format	HDF5 files
Size	~ 11 GB
Keywords	electromagnetic, calorimeter, electron
Version	Not applicable
Date of Repository Submission	2022-03-17
Necessary Software	Python package H5py can be used to open the files
Rights	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International
Re-use	Pre-existing dataset
Data privacy	The dataset contains no personal data

2.4 Dataset 4 - LEMURS

Table 4: LEMURS Metadata

Field	Description
Title	LEMURS dataset: Large-scale multi-detector ElectroMagnetic Universal Representation of Showers
Responsible Partner	CERN
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.17045561
Dataset Description	Photon (gamma) showers are presented, developing in 5 different electromagnetic detectors (Par04SiW, Par04SciPb, ODD, FCCeeCLD, FCCeeALLEGRO) using custom scoring mechanism (Universal Representation of Showers). Nearly 1M showers per detector are simulated in a Universal Representation, which was implemented first in Par04 extended example of Geant4, and used also by dataset 2 of CaloChallenge. A file structure is slightly changed with respect to CaloChallenge files. Wide range of energies and angles are provided. Energy range differs for experiments on electron-positron colliders (FCCee*, up to 100 GeV) and for hadron colliders (Par04* and ODD, up to 1 TeV).
Work Package	WP3
Related Use Case	Particle physics
Source	The datasets are produced using GEANT4, a physics-based Monte Carlo Simulator
Processing	No specific pre-processing is required.
Repository	Zenodo
Language	English
Code List	Not applicable
Type	Voxelised point cloud data
Format	HDF5 files
Size	~ 60 GB
Keywords	electromagnetic, calorimeter, photon
Version	Not applicable
Date of Repository Submission	2025-09-03
Necessary Software	Python package H5py can be used to open the files
Rights	Creative Commons Attribution Share Alike 4.0 International
Re-use	Pre-existing dataset
Data privacy	The dataset contains no personal data

2.5 Dataset 5 - STUBA Criticality benchmarks

Table 5: Criticality Benchmarks Metadata

Field	Description
Title	500 Benchmark Criticality Experiments (500BCE)
Responsible Partner	STUBA
DOI	Not yet applicable
Dataset Description	500BCE contains experimental and computational results 500 selected criticality experiments. Experimental results, consisting of multiplication factor, were obtained from the original documentation of the experiments. Computational results (multiplication factor and sensitivity profile) were obtained with SCALE's TSUNAMI module, using updated versions of original computational models of the experiments. All experiments are compiled in a list, which maps their characteristics.
Work Package	WP3
Related Use Case	Nuclear
Source	Models, descriptions and results of experiments were obtained from DICE. Computational results were obtained using current version of SCALE's TSUNAMI module.
Processing	Models were updated for current SCALE version. Descriptions of experiments were transformed into a simple characteristics map including experimental and computational results of multiplication factor.
Repository	To be determined
Language	English
Code List	Not applicable
Type	SCALE input and structured tabular dataset
Format	.xlsx , .txt, .sdf
Size	Complete dataset ~ 10 GB
Keywords	SCALE input, sensitivity profile, model parameters
Version	N/A
Date of Repository Submission	To be determined
Necessary Software	Javapeno (optional for visualization)
Rights	Private data, property of STUBA. Access provided to project partners only.
Re-use	Pre-existing dataset
Data privacy	The dataset contains no personal data

2.6 Dataset 6 - Simulation Output and Conclusion

Table 6: USTUTT Simulation - Output and Conclusion Dataset Metadata

Field	Description
Title	USTUTT Simulation - Output and Conclusion Dataset
Responsible Partner	IKE, University of Stuttgart
DOI	Not yet applicable
Dataset Description	Dataset containing results from 5000 COCOMO simulations. These simulations investigate the effect of varying porosities on nuclear debris bed coolability. Each simulation is classified as Melted, Quenched, or Timed Out. Timed Out refers to simulations exceeding 7200 seconds runtime. The dataset includes input parameters, final outcomes, and quenching times, if the simulation quenches.
Work Package	WP3
Related Use Case	Nuclear
Source	Generated using COCOMO simulations executed on the HLRS cluster, as well as on the IKE GPU cluster.
Processing	Simulation outputs were post-processed. Final conclusions were extracted from HTML output files, based on the simulation stopping conditions.
Repository	To be determined
Language	English
Code List	N/A
Type	Structured tabular dataset
Format	XLSX
Size	Several MBs
Keywords	Porosity, Melted, Quenched, Timed Out, Quenching Time
Version	v1.1
Date of Repository Submission	To be determined
Necessary Software	Python with standard data analysis libraries (e.g., pandas)
Rights	Private dataset. Property of IKE, University of Stuttgart. Access is restricted to project partners only.
Re-use	New dataset
Data privacy	The dataset contains no personal data

2.7 Dataset 7 - Simulation TimeSeries Analysis

Table 7: USTUTT Simulation - Time Series Dataset Metadata

Field	Description
Title	USTUTT Simulation - Time Series Dataset
Responsible Partner	IKE, University of Stuttgart
DOI	Not yet applicable
Dataset Description	Time-series dataset from COCOMO simulations, investigating nuclear debris bed coolability. Contains the temporal evolution of key thermodynamic and heat-transfer parameters. Enables analysis of parameter influence on the final simulation outcomes.
Related Use Case	Nuclear
Source	Generated using COCOMO simulations executed on the HLRS cluster, as well as on the IKE GPU cluster.
Processing	Extracted and curated from simulation balance output CSV files. Only the important physical parameters were retained for time series analysis.
Repository	To be determined
Language	English
Code List	N/A
Type	Structured tabular dataset
Format	XLSX
Size	Several TBs
Keywords	Time, ep (internal energy of solid particles), qgini (integral gas heat inflow), pow (system internal power from decay heat)
Version	v1.1
Date of Repository Submission	To be determined
Necessary Software	Python data analysis libraries; VisIt (optional for visualization)
Rights	Private dataset. Property of IKE, University of Stuttgart. Access is restricted to project partners only.
Re-use	New dataset
Data privacy	The dataset contains no personal data

2.8 Dataset 8 - NRG PALLAS Thermal Hydraulic

Table 8: NRG PALLAS - Thermal Hydraulics

Field	Description
Title	Thermal hydraulics: reactor operational behaviour and transients
Responsible Partner	NRG PALLAS
DOI	Not yet applicable
Dataset Description	Time series data for multiple reactor states with normal operational behaviour and labeled transients
Work Package	WP3
Related Use Case	Nuclear
Source	Generated using TRACE code
Processing	CSV files for the relevant parameters are presented.
Repository	To be determined
Language	English
Code List	N/A
Type	Structured tabular dataset
Format	labeled CSV's
Size	Several GBs
Keywords	Time, reactor state, accident analysis
Version	N/A
Date of Repository Submission	To be determined
Necessary Software	Standard CSV processing
Rights	Open data
Re-use	New dataset
Data privacy	The dataset contains no personal data

2.9 Dataset 9 - NRG PALLAS Core optimization

Table 9: NRG PALLAS - Core optimization

Field	Description
Title	Dataset for core optimization
Responsible Partner	NRG PALLAS
DOI	Not yet applicable
Dataset Description	Dataset describing different reactor cores. The reactor core loading is represented by the uranium mass of the fuel assemblies. For each core loading different core parameters are computed to describe it, such as the neutron flux, core power, and effective multiplication factor.
Work Package	WP2
Related Use Case	Nuclear
Source	The dataset is generated using the MGRAC code and the BEAVRS reactor simulation benchmark.
Processing	Results were post-processed to extract the data of interest.
Repository	To be determined
Language	English
Code List	N/A
Type	Structured tabular dataset
Format	Labeled CSV, .txt
Size	Several GBs
Keywords	Core loading, fuel assembly, thermal and total flux effective multiplication factor, power, axial offset
Version	v1.1
Date of Repository Submission	To be determined
Necessary Software	Standard CSV processing
Rights	Open data
Re-use	New dataset
Data privacy	The dataset contains no personal data

3. Compliance with FAIR Data Principles

The data management framework of TURING is structured around the FAIR principles, ensuring that research data and associated digital artefacts are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable [7]. The implementation of these principles is aligned with the Open Science obligations defined in the Horizon Europe Model Grant Agreement [3].

FAIR data principles¹ provide a structured approach for improving the discoverability, accessibility, interoperability, and reuse of research data. In the context of European research data management practice, project data should be made as open as possible while remaining as restricted as necessary, taking into account legal, ethical, and contractual obligations.

A distinction is therefore made between open data and FAIR data. Open data are freely accessible and reusable without restrictive licensing conditions, whereas datasets may still comply with FAIR principles even when access is limited, provided that data and metadata are properly documented and managed to enable discovery and controlled reuse when permitted.

Within TURING, FAIR compliance is operationalised through the assignment of persistent identifiers, the use of structured metadata standards, the adoption of interoperable data formats, and clearly defined access conditions for both open and restricted datasets. Regardless of access conditions, the TURING data management policy ensures that all datasets produced or processed within the project are handled consistently in alignment with FAIR principles.

Figure 1: TURING FAIR data principles

¹<https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

Applying FAIR principles ensures that datasets remain findable, accessible under appropriate conditions, interoperable, and reusable, thereby facilitating efficient data discovery, sharing, and reuse across research and innovation communities while supporting transparency and reproducibility and maximizing the long-term value of project data assets.

As described in the previous section, the datasets to be generated and used within the TURING project have been introduced. In alignment with Open Science practices, the consortium aims to make datasets openly available whenever feasible. However, certain datasets may remain confidential or accessible only under controlled conditions due to legal, contractual, security, or commercial considerations. The implementation of FAIR principles within the project will be further detailed in the following subsections.

3.1 Findable Data

The first step in enabling data (re)use is ensuring that datasets can be easily found. Both data and metadata should therefore be discoverable by humans and machines. Machine-readable metadata plays a crucial role in enabling automatic discovery of datasets and related services and constitutes an essential component of the FAIR data management process. Within the TURING project, measures will therefore be implemented to ensure effective dataset discoverability and traceability. In accordance with the FAIR data principles, the project addresses the following requirements:

- **F1. (Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier.** Datasets and digital resources made publicly available will be assigned persistent identifiers through trusted repositories, allowing reliable citation and long-term discoverability.
- **F2. Data are described with rich metadata.** Datasets will be accompanied by comprehensive metadata describing their origin, structure, processing methods, and usage conditions, facilitating discovery and enabling effective understanding and reuse.
- **F3. (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource.** Publicly shareable datasets and associated metadata will be deposited in searchable online repositories to enable discovery by research and innovation communities.
- **F4. Metadata specify the data identifier.** Metadata records will explicitly include dataset identifiers, ensuring a clear and persistent linkage between metadata and the data resources they describe.

Datasets intended for public dissemination will be deposited in the trusted open-access repository Zenodo [1]. Where datasets contain confidential or sensitive information necessary for project activities, they will be securely stored within partner-managed infrastructures with access restricted to authorised consortium members. Nevertheless, FAIR principles will be applied consistently to all datasets to ensure proper documentation and controlled discoverability throughout the project lifecycle [7].

Structured dataset documentation for publicly released data follows the DataCite Metadata Schema to ensure standardised description and persistent identification of research outputs [2]. Zenodo assigns persistent Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs), guaranteeing long-term accessibility, citability, and compliance with FAIR data management practices.

In cases where datasets are exceptionally large (e.g., exceeding practical repository limits, such as >50 GB per record) and cannot be fully replicated in Zenodo, the datasets will be stored in trusted institutional or partner-managed repositories. In such cases, a descriptive metadata record and associated documentation will still be published via Zenodo and assigned a DOI, ensuring persistent referencing, discoverability, and compliance with FAIR principles.

TURING will apply a standardized naming convention for datasets generated and used throughout the project to ensure consistency, traceability, and easier identification of dataset versions across project activities. The naming convention will include the following elements:

1. The short name of the contributing partner or use case.
2. The name or description of the dataset.
3. The project acronym (TURING).
4. The dataset upload or release date.
5. A version identifier that is incremented whenever a dataset is updated or revised.

This results in dataset identifiers following the format:

```
ShortName_DatasetName_TURING_yyyy.mm.dd_vX.X_[.extension]
```

This naming convention ensures that datasets remain easily identifiable, traceable, and properly versioned throughout the project lifecycle.

3.2 Accessible Data

Making data accessible requires that users clearly understand how datasets can be retrieved once they have been discovered. Within the TURING project, accessibility procedures will ensure effective sharing of research outputs while protecting confidential or sensitive information where necessary.

In accordance with the FAIR data principles, the following measures will be applied:

- **A1. (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol.** Publicly available datasets will be deposited in trusted repositories such as Zenodo, which provide standardized communication protocols allowing datasets to be retrieved using persistent identifiers.

- **A1.1 The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable.** Public datasets will be accessible through open and widely implemented protocols supported by repository platforms, ensuring accessibility without reliance on proprietary technologies.
- **A1.2 The protocol allows authentication and authorization where necessary.** When datasets contain confidential or sensitive information, access will be limited to authorized users through authentication and authorization procedures managed by project partners.
- **A2. Metadata remain accessible even when the data are no longer available.** Metadata describing project datasets will remain accessible whenever possible, ensuring discoverability and documentation even if direct access to the underlying data becomes restricted or discontinued.

Datasets intended for public dissemination will be deposited in the Zenodo repository to enable open access and long-term preservation. Datasets that cannot be openly shared due to legal, contractual, security, or commercial constraints will be securely stored within partner-managed infrastructures, with access granted only to authorized consortium members. Whenever possible, metadata describing restricted datasets will still be published to support dataset discovery.

Ensuring accessibility within the TURING project extends beyond datasets and also applies to scientific publications resulting from the project. In accordance with the Horizon Europe Model Grant Agreement, all peer-reviewed scientific publications arising from project activities will be made openly accessible. When determining the appropriate open-access route, the consortium will take into account data protection requirements, confidentiality obligations, and intellectual property considerations.

The consortium will primarily follow the green open-access model, enabling publications to be made openly available through repositories within allowed embargo periods, either in the final publisher-formatted version or, where required by licensing conditions, in the author-accepted manuscript (non-formatted version). In cases where green open access is not suitable or where timely dissemination is required, the gold open-access model may be adopted.

Prior to any public dissemination of research outputs, an internal assessment will be carried out to identify potential conflicts with intellectual property rights, commercial interests, or security constraints, ensuring that open-access obligations are fulfilled while safeguarding the legitimate interests of the consortium and its partners.

Access to datasets may also be limited when required to protect intellectual property rights, commercial interests, personal data, or security-sensitive information of project partners. Such restrictions will be applied in line with the Grant Agreement and consortium arrangements while ensuring that dataset documentation and metadata remain available to facilitate discoverability and potential future reuse.

The consortium will periodically assess whether parts of restricted datasets can be made publicly available during or after the project lifetime, in line with the principle of making data as open as possible while respecting necessary restrictions.

3.3 Interoperable Data

Interoperability ensures that datasets can be integrated with other datasets and can operate with applications and workflows used by researchers and project partners. Within the TURING project, datasets will be structured and documented to support exchange, integration, and reuse across different research environments and technical platforms.

In accordance with the FAIR data principles, the following measures will be applied:

- **I1. (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.** Datasets will be stored, whenever feasible, using widely adopted and machine-readable formats commonly used within AI and data analytics communities to facilitate long-term usability and interoperability.
- **I2. (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles.** Where applicable, commonly accepted vocabularies and standard terminologies will be used to ensure consistency and compatibility between datasets and tools across project partners.
- **I3. (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data.** Metadata will include references to related datasets, software components, publications, or project deliverables whenever appropriate, enabling traceability and integration across project outputs.

To support interoperability and consistent data exchange among project partners and external users, TURING datasets will be accompanied by standardized metadata describing dataset structure, origin, processing, and usage conditions. A common metadata template will be adopted across the project to ensure datasets remain understandable, interoperable, and reusable across different platforms and research environments.

Table 10 presents the metadata template that will be used to document datasets generated within the TURING project.

Table 10: TURING Metadata table

Field	Description
Title	Name of the dataset
Responsible Partner	Name of the partner responsible for the data created
Dataset Identifier	Dataset internal reference number
DOI	Digital Object Identifier (if applicable)
Dataset Description	A brief description of the dataset
Related Use Case	Weather, nuclear or particle physics
Work Package	Associated work package
Source	How the data have been generated
Processing	How the data have been processed
Repository	The repository where the data will be uploaded
Language	All languages used in the dataset
Code List	Explanation of codes or abbreviations used
Type	Types of the data
Format	Formats of the data
Size	An approximation of the size of the dataset
Keywords	Keywords describing the content of the data
Version	Unique identifier for each version of the dataset
Date of Repository Submission	Release date (preferred format yyyy-mm-dd)
Necessary Software	Necessary software needed to create, view or analyse data
Rights	Where and how the data can be accessed by other researchers
Re-use	Pre-existing data or collected within the project
Data privacy	Indicate privacy concerns and data protection measures

The adoption of this metadata structure will support interoperability across project partners and facilitate dataset reuse beyond the project duration by ensuring datasets are consistently documented and technically understandable across different platforms and research contexts.

3.4 Reusable Data

Data reusability is a key objective of the TURING data management approach, ensuring that datasets can support validation of project results and enable further research and innovation beyond the project lifetime. To facilitate reuse, datasets will be properly documented, quality controlled, and accompanied by clear usage conditions.

In accordance with the FAIR data principles, the following measures will be applied:

- **R1. (Meta)data are richly described with accurate and relevant attributes.** Datasets generated within TURING will be accompanied by sufficient metadata and documentation describing data origin, structure, processing steps, and usage conditions to enable interpretation and reuse.
- **R1.1. (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license.** Publicly shared datasets will include clear licensing terms specifying reuse conditions. Open licenses

compatible with Horizon Europe Open Science practices will be used whenever possible while respecting intellectual property rights and partner obligations.

- **R1.2. (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance information.** Information describing how datasets were generated, processed, and transformed will be documented to ensure traceability and proper interpretation by future users.
- **R1.3. (Meta)data meet relevant community standards.** Whenever applicable, datasets will follow commonly accepted formats and standards used within the relevant research and industrial communities to promote compatibility and reuse.

Examples of relevant community standards include GRIB, NetCDF, or Zarr formats for atmospheric and climate data; HDF5 for high-energy physics datasets; and structured tabular formats such as CSV or XLSX for simulation outputs. Where applicable, interoperable model exchange formats may also be adopted for AI-related artefacts to facilitate reuse and cross-platform compatibility.

Public datasets will be deposited in the Zenodo repository as soon as they are ready for dissemination and will remain accessible after project completion, subject to repository policies. Nevertheless, restrictions such as embargo periods or limitations imposed by scientific publishers or conference organisers may apply and will be assessed on a case-by-case basis.

A Data Quality Assurance Process (DQAP) will be progressively established and applied throughout the project to ensure that datasets generated or collected meet quality requirements necessary for reuse. The quality assurance process will aim to guarantee data validity, reliability, integrity, timeliness, and completeness, enabling, whenever possible, the reproduction of results reported in project publications.

Reuse conditions may also be influenced by legal, contractual, ethical, or commercial constraints. In such cases, access conditions and licensing terms will be clearly documented, while metadata describing the datasets will remain available to support discoverability and potential future reuse.

4. Allocation of Resources

In this preliminary version of the Data Management Plan, the allocation of resources reflects the anticipated data management needs of the TURING project, based on the datasets currently identified and the expected data volumes and processing requirements. Accordingly, the necessary storage infrastructure and technical specifications are planned in advance and described in the following sections of this document.

As the project progresses and additional datasets are generated or requirements evolve, resource needs related to data storage, curation, documentation, and long-term preservation may be further refined. Any significant changes in resource allocation will be documented in the updated versions of the DMP planned at later stages of the project.

FIS will utilise its existing 378 TB storage pool and the new H200 GPU nodes to fulfil the requirements of Task 5.1 (Computing Infrastructure Setup).

The existing High-Performance Computing (HPC) Trdina infrastructure was previously funded through prior (EU) structural and research initiatives. Consequently, no additional capital expenditure for the current hardware is requested from the TURING budget. The planned upgrade to NVIDIA H200NVL nodes is likewise funded through separate EU-supported projects. The use of this equipment is provided at no cost to the consortium, representing a significant optimisation of project resources.

While the hardware itself is a prior investment, all costs related to the setup, configuration, maintenance, and integration of the infrastructure for TURING-specific tasks (Task 5.1) are fully funded by the EU. These operational activities are covered through the allocation of PMs defined in the project budget, ensuring that FIS technical staff are fully funded to provide infrastructure support, implement security protocols, and manage Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) data principles throughout the project lifecycle.

The main technical characteristics of the storage and computing infrastructure allocated to the TURING project are summarised below.

A) Storage Infrastructure (HPC Trdina)

Total main storage capacity amounts to 378 TB, of which approximately 24 TB is currently utilised, leaving over 350 TB available for project-specific data.

The storage backend consists of three dedicated storage servers, each equipped with 2× Intel Xeon Cascade Lake (CLX) 4210 processors (10 cores each), providing a total of 60 CPU cores across the storage cluster, and a cumulative 768 GB of RAM. All storage and compute nodes are interconnected via a high-speed 100 GbE local network to ensure rapid data throughput.

B) Compute Infrastructure

Current HPC Trdina nodes include:

- Head Node: 2× AMD EPYC 7501 CPUs (64 cores total), 1024 GB RAM.

- Compute Nodes (3×): 192 CPU cores in total (AMD EPYC 7501), 1536 GB RAM.
- GPU Node: 4× NVIDIA Tesla V100 GPUs (32 GB memory each).

The upcoming TURING infrastructure upgrade includes two Supermicro AS-5126GS-TNRT servers featuring:

- 4× NVIDIA H200NVL GPUs (141 GB memory per GPU),
- AMD EPYC Turin CPUs, and
- DDR5-6400 system memory.

5. Data Security

The TURING project adopts a security-by-design approach for the protection of all datasets generated or processed during the project. Data security measures are defined in accordance with the sensitivity and access classification of the datasets, ensuring the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of data throughout their lifecycle. These measures combine technical infrastructure safeguards with organisational procedures applied across the consortium.

All consortium partners are responsible for handling project data in accordance with institutional security policies and applicable legal requirements. Datasets classified as Confidential or Closed Access are subject to stricter handling procedures, including restricted access to authorised personnel only.

The technical infrastructure supporting data storage and processing within TURING is implemented and maintained by FIS under Task 5.1. The main security controls are summarised below.

1. Access Control

FIS implements a strict identity-based access control system based on Linux group-restricted permissions. All project data are stored in a dedicated directory owned by `root:turing`, ensuring that global project security rules cannot be modified by individual users.

A *classified permission model* (`rwxrwx---`) is applied, restricting access exclusively to verified members of the `turing` system group.

2. Directory-Level Restrictions

To prevent accidental data loss and ensure collaborative integrity, FIS applies advanced Linux file system mechanisms:

- All newly created files automatically inherit the `turing` group ID, ensuring immediate availability to authorised consortium members.
- The *sticky bit* (`+t`) is applied to shared directories, allowing all project members to read and modify files while restricting deletion privileges to the original file owner or system administrators.

User access to data is performed via Apptainer (formerly Singularity), which isolates user software environments. The data repository must be explicitly bound to the container at runtime to become accessible.

3. Authentication Mechanisms

Access to the FIS High-Performance Computing (HPC) infrastructure is secured through SSH key-based authentication. If required by evolving project security needs, an additional two-factor authentication (2FA) layer (e.g., TOTP or Duo) can be enabled through institutional identity provider services, in line with FIS security policies for high-performance computing environments.

4. Activity Monitoring and Audit Logging

Accountability is ensured through an ownership-based audit model, where each file retains the creator's user identity as file owner. This provides traceability of dataset creation and modification activities.

In addition, standard HPC scheduling tools (e.g., Slurm) and system-level logs are used to monitor job execution and data access patterns.

5. Data Encryption

All remote access to the HPC infrastructure and data repositories is conducted using encrypted communication protocols (e.g., SSH/SFTP), ensuring protection of data in transit.

Internal data transfers between compute and storage nodes take place over a secured high-speed 100 GbE network.

6. Compliance with Legal and Ethical Requirements

As the leader of Task 5.1, FIS enforces security protocols aligned with the project's ethical framework. Access to datasets is limited strictly to authorised personnel, preventing unauthorised disclosure of sensitive or proprietary information.

The infrastructure setup supports data handling in accordance with FAIR principles and Horizon Europe requirements.

7. Version Control and Backup

FIS implements systematic dataset management and backup procedures to ensure data durability and recoverability. Consortium partners are instructed to store results and trained models directly within the project repository so that they are included in regular backup routines.

Project source code and configuration files may be managed through the project Git repository to support version control and collaborative development.

In the event of a data security incident, appropriate mitigation and reporting procedures will be followed in accordance with institutional policies and applicable regulations. As this deliverable represents the preliminary version of the Data Management Plan, data security measures may be refined in subsequent updates of the DMP as the project evolves.

6. Ethics, Privacy, and Trustworthy AI

The TURING project develops and evaluates AI methodologies and therefore places particular emphasis on ethical conduct, privacy protection, and trustworthy AI principles. Ethical considerations are embedded throughout the project lifecycle, from data collection and model development to evaluation and validation activities. The project is conducted in accordance with the ethical principles and research integrity requirements defined in the Grant Agreement and applicable international, European, and national legislation.

1. Compliance with Legal and Regulatory Frameworks

All data processing activities within TURING comply with the GDPR and relevant national data protection laws of the participating countries. Where applicable, the project also considers regulatory requirements in partner countries outside the EU.

The consortium acknowledges the regulatory framework established by the European Union Artificial Intelligence Act (AI Act) [5] and adopts a risk-aware approach to the development and evaluation of AI systems. While TURING focuses on research and innovation activities, the consortium monitors evolving AI regulatory requirements and considers transparency, documentation, human oversight, and robustness principles in line with emerging EU AI governance frameworks.

2. Privacy and Personal Data Protection

The majority of datasets processed within TURING consist of scientific, simulation-based, and experimental data (e.g., atmospheric data, physics simulations, nuclear benchmarks) and do not contain personal data.

Where personal data may be processed (e.g., contact details for project communication, stakeholder engagement, or event participation), such processing is strictly limited to clearly defined project-related purposes. Data minimisation principles are applied, and appropriate technical and organisational measures are implemented to ensure confidentiality, integrity, and availability.

All personal data processing activities comply with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation – GDPR) [4]. Lawful processing grounds are identified where required, including informed consent where applicable. Data subjects' rights, including access, rectification, and deletion, are respected in accordance with applicable legislation.

3. Trustworthy AI and Responsible GenAI Development

The development and evaluation of GenAI models within TURING are guided by core trustworthy AI principles, including:

- Transparency and explainability of AI-generated outputs, where technically feasible;
- Technical robustness and reliability of models;

- Human oversight during validation and evaluation processes;
- Identification and mitigation of bias and unintended harmful effects;
- Consideration of potential hallucination risks and misuse scenarios.

Risk assessment mechanisms are applied to identify and mitigate potential ethical risks, including dual-use concerns and unintended societal impacts.

4. **Data Governance and Access Control**

Datasets generated or processed within TURING are managed according to the access classifications defined in this Data Management Plan (DMP) (Open Access, Confidential, Closed Access). Confidential and Closed datasets are accessible only to authorised personnel under controlled conditions, including, where applicable, Non-Disclosure Agreements (NDAs).

Security-by-design and data protection-by-design approaches are applied in coordination with the technical infrastructure described in previous sections.

5. **Ethical Oversight and Governance Structure**

Ethical aspects of the TURING project are monitored throughout the project duration. An appropriate governance structure, including oversight mechanisms defined in the Description of Action, supports compliance with ethical, legal, and trustworthy AI [6] requirements.

Regular internal reviews and reporting mechanisms ensure alignment with ethical standards and regulatory developments. Any significant updates to ethical, privacy, or AI governance measures will be reflected in subsequent versions of this Data Management Plan.

6.1 Ethics Advisory Board (EAB)

To ensure continuous ethical oversight and alignment with applicable regulatory frameworks, the TURING project is supported by an Ethics Advisory Board (EAB).

The Ethics Advisory Board consists of members with expertise in research ethics, data protection, artificial intelligence governance, and relevant domain-specific areas. The EAB provides independent guidance to the consortium on ethical, legal, and societal aspects related to data processing, AI model development, and Generative AI deployment within the project.

The main responsibilities of the Ethics Advisory Board include:

- Reviewing project activities that may raise ethical, privacy, or dual-use concerns;
- Advising on compliance with the GDPR, the AI Act, and other applicable regulatory frameworks;
- Providing recommendations regarding risk mitigation strategies for bias, hallucination risks, and potential misuse of GenAI systems;
- Supporting the identification of emerging ethical risks as the project evolves.

The Ethics Advisory Board operates in coordination with the Project Coordinator, the Data Manager, and the designated Ethics Manager. While the Ethics Manager is responsible for the day-to-day monitoring of ethical compliance and the implementation of ethics-related procedures within the project, the Ethics Advisory Board provides independent guidance and may issue recommendations to the consortium where necessary. Its oversight contributes to ensuring that TURING activities remain aligned with Horizon Europe ethical requirements, the EU regulatory framework, and trustworthy AI principles.

As this deliverable represents the preliminary version of the Data Management Plan, the ethical and AI governance measures described above may be further refined as the project progresses and regulatory frameworks evolve. Updates will be incorporated in the revised DMP versions planned at later stages of the project.

7. Conclusions

This deliverable presents the preliminary version of the DMP for the TURING project. It establishes the framework for the responsible, secure, and FAIR-compliant management of datasets generated and processed throughout the project lifecycle.

The DMP defines the dataset classification scheme, metadata structure, access conditions, security measures, and ethical governance mechanisms adopted by the consortium. Particular attention is given to privacy protection, data security, and the responsible development and evaluation of Generative AI technologies, in alignment with GDPR requirements and the emerging regulatory framework of the EU Artificial Intelligence Act.

The allocation of computational and storage resources has been anticipated based on the expected data volumes and project needs, ensuring that adequate infrastructure and operational support are available from the outset. Security-by-design and data protection-by-design principles are integrated into the technical infrastructure and governance processes.

As a living document, this DMP will be reviewed and updated during the project duration. Revised versions are planned M18 and M36, reflecting newly generated datasets, evolving technical requirements, regulatory developments, and lessons learned during project implementation. Through these updates, the TURING consortium will ensure continued alignment with Horizon Europe Open Science principles and responsible AI practices.

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